

EHMA 2024

Shaping and managing
innovative health ecosystems

5-7 June 2024 - Bucharest, Romania

ABSTRACT BOOK

Institutul Național de Management
al Serviciilor de Sănătate

The European Health Management Association

The European Health Management Association (EHMA) is a not-for-profit membership organisation. Active since 1982, our vision is excellent health management for a healthy Europe.

We support the spread of knowledge on effective health management. Our actions focus on health management capacity and capabilities and aim to support the successful implementation of health policy and practice. We are a recognised and respected amplifier of best practices in the evolution of health management, with a European and global reach. Through our efforts, we make a difference across Europe to improve health for all citizens.

We are open to all those committed to improving health and healthcare. We play a crucial role in engaging with the full European health management ecosystem. We are a highly accessible and well-established place where people can debate and engage in issues that affect them, where they feel they can advocate for change, and find solutions. Through our members and networks, we reach local, regional, national, and international levels.

About the EHMA Conference

The EHMA Conference is Europe's preeminent conference on health management. Each year it gathers the full healthcare ecosystem, including health managers and leaders, healthcare professionals, researchers, academics, industry representatives, and decision-makers from Europe, and beyond.

The EHMA Conference provides a platform to discuss the latest health management research, tools and evidence from renowned researchers, academics and professionals. It is concerned on translating research into practice. It creates opportunities for dialogue and exchange on solutions to ensure the sustainability and resilience of health systems.

The European Health Management Conference 2024

EHMA 2024 is the 29th edition of our Annual Conference. This year's conference theme 'Shaping and managing innovative health ecosystems' encompasses the entire spectrum of health megatrends. From the digital transformation of healthcare systems and services, to the ever-growing importance of sustainability, and the evolving skill sets required by the healthcare workforce, we aim to explore how the health sector is adapting to these changes.

We emphasise an ecosystem approach, promoting collaboration among stakeholders. Our aim is to facilitate dialogue on how different health care actors can work together and leverage each other's strengths to drive innovation and address pressing challenges.

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Implementing of a model of digital healthcare ecosystem based on blockchain technology – a pilot study

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Blockchain represents a technology that provides significant possibilities for improving the functioning of digital health systems. The main advantages of blockchain, which can be utilised to ensure the security of health data as well as information exchanged by stakeholders of the healthcare ecosystem, are: data access flexibility, privacy, decentralised storage, transparency, immutability, authentication, disintermediation, verifiability, programmability, and interconnection.

For the previously proposed model of a digital health ecosystem based on blockchain technology, we have developed a decentralised Web3 application, which demonstrates key functionalities for the patients, doctors and administrative personnel who participate in the business transactions and data exchange between identified stakeholders. The main technologies used in the application development included Ethereum blockchain network, Interplanetary File System (IPFS), MongoDB Atlas and JavaScript. Metamask add-on software was used for coupling the application with Ethereum accounts and corresponding smart contracts deployed in blockchain.

The developed application was implemented and monitored in a private healthcare organisation in the Republic of Serbia. The testing period lasted for 30 days, and it included the phases of initiation, stabilisation and functional use. During that period, the patients and hospital personnel had the opportunity to actively use the application and its components. The test data were fictional, in accordance with the patient data and institution's operations protection policies. Evaluation of the proposed model included both evaluation of implemented application and identification of key factors that influence the implementation process, including the mapping of important cause-and-effect relationships.

Applied technical solutions, which ensure the functioning of the proposed model, were tested and evaluated in relation to system quality, information quality, service quality, system use, and user satisfaction through defined appropriate key performance identifiers. The analysis of the results obtained by surveying in the post-implementation period indicates high satisfaction with the application of the proposed software and technical solutions. Further analysis of the evaluation data identified the key motivating factors for the adoption of blockchain technology in the healthcare sector, namely: expected effort, social impact, price value and expected performance. These constructs should be the basis for a promotional strategy for the application of blockchain technology in the healthcare sector of the Republic of Serbia.